

ENSURING FOOD SAFETY IS THE NEED OF THE HOUR

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ABSTRACT

This article is about ensuring food safety, solving food safety problems and solutions. By safe food, we usually mean high-quality, environmentally friendly food, without genetically modified organisms (GMOs), such as pesticides. We mean products without harmful elements related to food.

Food safety is one of the most urgent tasks facing the countries of the world. The UN is also saying today that it is time to completely change the approach to food production and distribution. After all, in an ideal situation, agriculture, forestry and fisheries are able to provide everyone with food and create a source of income for people, as in the brochure. Moreover, in such a case, both agriculture will develop in the interests of people, and environmental protection measures will be implemented. Food is one of the most important elements in human life [1].

Consumers always want to get quality and safe products. By safe food, we usually mean high-quality, environmentally friendly, non-GMO (genetically modified organism) products, products that do not contain harmful elements related to food, such as pesticides. Food security is one of the main problems of humanity and determines the health, development and well-being of nations. The quality of food consumed by the population is an important component of the level and quality of life of citizens and has a serious impact on environmental protection, as well as on the socio-economic and demographic situation of the country. Food security has a significant impact on the positive development of the demographic situation, which allows maintaining the health of the country's population. Safe nutrition prolongs life, helps children grow and develop, prevents many diseases, thereby ensuring the health of the nation. Today, when the production of artificial products is increasing day by day, the control over food safety cannot be allowed to weaken [2].

Food security is one of the main problems of humanity and determines the health, development and well-being of nations. The quality of food consumed by the population is an important component of the level and quality of life of citizens and has a serious impact on environmental protection, as well as on the socio-economic and demographic situation of the country. Food security has a significant impact on the positive development of the demographic situation, which allows maintaining the health of the country's population. Safe

nutrition prolongs life, helps children grow and develop, prevents many diseases, thereby ensuring the health of the nation. Today, when the production of artificial products is increasing day by day, the control over food safety cannot be allowed to weaken. Food security of the country is a socio-economic and legal situation in which the possibility of continuously providing the population with essential consumer products without endangering the health of the population at the level of physical requirements is guaranteed. In other words, food that does not pose a threat to the current and future generations is considered safe. Therefore, today, the objectivity of product quality control, in turn, guarantees its safety for the health of all mankind, so the problems related to this field cannot be looked at superficially. In-depth disclosure of our research topic, disclosure of problems in the field, making necessary proposals requires analysis of legislative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In Article 17 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Sanitary and Epidemiological Peace of the Population", citizens receive information from state administration bodies, local state authorities, as well as from bodies implementing state sanitary control, about the sanitary-epidemiological situation and the state of human habitat, from legal entities. and it is established that individual entrepreneurs have the right to receive information about the safety and quality of the product, as well as the work being performed and the services provided. It follows that every citizen has the right to have sufficient information about the safety requirements of the products he consumes. Also, in our legislation, the concept of "food product safety" is defined: "food product safety is compliance of the food product with sanitary, veterinary, veterinary-sanitary, phytosanitary rules and norms" [3].

Recently, another initiative was taken by the UN in this field. That is, a global campaign to combat food waste was announced. This also serves food safety. According to the information of the Organization for the Environment (UNEP) of this structure, 1.3 bln. Tons of food products are thrown away. In order to put an end to such an illogical state of waste of blessings, first of all, it is proposed to change the conditions of their storage. It is known that agriculture is the leading sector of the economy in Uzbekistan. It employs 3.6 million people, i.e. 27% of all employed in the economy. The sector's share in GDP is 32%, while the land used in the sector occupies 45% of the territory of the republic. At present, more than 180 types of agricultural and food products are exported to more than 80 countries. Another noteworthy point is that the cluster method of production in agriculture has been introduced and is gaining popularity. This is confirmed by the fact that 62% of agricultural land areas are covered by cotton and textile, 8% by livestock and 7.5% by fruit and vegetable production [4].

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